

The Effectiveness of Using Orton- Gillingham Approach to Teach Reading Skill for Hearing Impaired Students at Integrated Schools in Jeddah

Lina Bin Saddiq

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 12, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Hearing Impairment, Orton- Gillingham Approach,Educational Computer,Hearing Impaired Students, Special Education, Expressive Language.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12734648</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to uncover the effectiveness of a computerized educational program based on Orton- Gillingham Approach in speaking training to develop expressive language among a sample of hearing-impaired students in light of the variable of gender (male, female) and age (4-5, 5-6, 6-7) years. To achieve the aim of the study, a sample of (30) male and female students was chosen by the intentional method from integration schools in Jeddah from the year 2019/2020, their ages ranged between (4-7) years, and they were distributed into two groups: the first experimental and the second control, with 15) male and female students for each group. Al-Amayyereh (1998) verbal expression scale was used,the educational computer program for speech training for the development of expressive language was prepared by researchers after verifying the authenticity of its content by appropriate methods.The results showed that there are statistically significant differences in the performance of students on the total score of the post-measurement of the level of expressive language, and in favor of the experimental group that underwent the program, which indicates the effectiveness of the computerized educational program in developing expressive language among students with mild hearing impairment.The results also showed that there were no differences in the post-test due to the gender variable, while the results indicated that there were differences in the post-test due to the age variable in the level of expressive language, and it was in favor of the age group (6-7) years, followed by the group (5-6) years.</i></p>

Introduction

Education technologies represent one of the most important modern educational approaches for people with special needs, which have been linked to addressing many of their educational problems, and the importance of following this approach in designing education for people with special needs to ensure that their characteristics, educational needs, type and nature of disability are taken into account.

People with special needs are part of the fabric of society, and their education represents an urgent educational demand that entails engaging in society, live their lives, and practice their activities with respect and appreciation, especially that if they have shortcomings in a certain aspect, they have strength and energy in other aspects, perhaps more than the ordinary Hence, it must be invested and properly employed (Abdel-Atty, 2010).

The importance of educational technologies for the hearing-impaired is becoming more and more important at the current time, which is witnessing an increasing growth in the use of educational technologies and technological devices. Education, which turns the teacher from instructing and transmitting knowledge into a guide and mentor to learners (Abu Al-Ula, 2017).

The general trend has also increased towards educational technologies and work to take advantage of these technological innovations, and modern technologies include studying by using the computer in the classroom, the laboratory, or even at home in the case of e-learning, using any place where the student can study in where the learner is using a mobile phone, this opens up new learning opportunities. It enables the student to learn across space and time, and the student in this study was enthusiastic about the new learning options provided by mobile technologies, and stated that it provides them with new study opportunities as well as provides flexibility to study at anytime and anywhere (Hlodan, 2010).

With the increasing interest in the education of persons with hearing impairment in recent years as a result of what international agreements, human rights and equality between members of society have called for, and their employment opportunities, and this is what applies to the provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in achieving the goal of "inclusive education" to ensure that students with disabilities have full access, on an equal basis with other students (Education Technology Portal, 2015).

Modern technologies contribute to the development of the educational level of the hearing-impaired, as their teaching requires more flexible classroom practices, or therapeutic activities that focus on strengths, and

the use of the capabilities available to this group, and aims to adapt the teaching of the hearing-impaired, despite enabling them to enable them to learn through educational technologies (Aqel, 2012).

Therefore, most international schools and universities for deaf and hard of hearing people, such as Gallaudet University in Washington, the School of the Deaf in California, and the Lyngston School in New York have relied on many different technical applications in teaching deaf and hard of hearing people at different educational levels (Mahmoud, 2015).

In light of the amazing progress in educational technologies for those with special needs in general and the hearing-impaired in particular, interest in improving the academic achievement of the hearing impaired has increased, especially through these available technologies and technological innovations, and the use of these materials and the exploitation of many materials for the hearing impaired, for example, the study of Al-Amer (2009) demonstrated that there is a correlation between the use of educational technologies and the level of achievement in Saudi educational institutions. The study by Jacobsen-Agar (2010) proved that hearing-impaired students prefer visual and sensory methods in relation to learning styles. When compared to their hearing peers, students with hearing disabilities can achieve higher levels of achievement when they are taught using visual tactile materials and visual kinematic materials, since the sense of vision is one of the senses that they depend on. As for the study (Al-Sayed, 2011), it was found that the use of technology has an effective impact on the development of achievement and reading ability of pupils for the hearing-impaired, while the studies of Mustafa, 2015, Yunus & Al-Sayed, 2006, Sweidan, Al-Jazzar, 2007, Al-Fayez, 2010), Tuma's study (2013) indicated on the importance of educational technology for students with hearing disabilities in improving the quality of education and increasing the efficiency of the educational process, in addition to avoiding falling into verbal communication, which helps the hearing impaired to comprehend in an easy way, and to work on the participation of the largest number of the learner's senses in the learning process in a way that compensates the handicapped for their disability, in addition to raising the interest of the hearing impaired and satisfying their needs, and the acquisition of scientific skills and the deepening of scientific experiences to provide opportunities for developing thinking skills on a large level. In addition to modifying the learners' behavior and forming new directions for them, and achieving learning within a framework of pleasure through an educational environment full of sensory stimuli.

The study problem and its questions

The current study aims to identify the extent of the effectiveness of a computerized educational program for developing expressive language among a sample of students with mild hearing disabilities, and specifically, the current study is trying to answer the following questions:

1. What is the effectiveness of an educational computer program based on Orton- Gillingham Approach for speech training in developing expressive language among a sample of students with mild hearing impairment in integration schools in Jeddah?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance in the development of expressive language between the control group ($\alpha = 0.05$) that did not undergo the training program and the experimental group that underwent the educational program?
3. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance in the development of expressive language among the group members ($\alpha=0.05$) due to the gender variable?
4. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance in the development of expressive language for members of the experimental group ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the variable of age?

The importance of the study

All psychological and educational theoretical frameworks affirm that the early stages of development from the child's life are of utmost importance for the child's development, adaptation and compatibility with society in all developmental areas in general and linguistic ones in particular. Therefore, the acquisition of language by children is one of the important aspects of the child's life because it is related to different areas of life, whether mental, social, emotional or even physical. His environment helps him express his needs and desires as well as helps him to understand the desires of others and helps him to obtain information from the individuals around him (Smith, 2007).

Hence, the importance of this study emerges in light of educational calls for attention to children with special needs, especially with regard to the educational-learning process, represented by the use of modern educational and computer technologies in their learning.

The importance of the current study appears in developing the expressive language of students with simple hearing impairment, due to the social, academic and emotional problems that these children suffer from as a result of the hearing impairment.

Previous Studies

Al-Saed et al. (2017) study entitled "Development of educational technologies for the hearing-impaired and their role in improving academic achievement in Saudi educational institutions (a comparative study in light of the experiences of some countries)"

Al-Tweijri study (2014) aimed at identifying the problems that teachers of the hearing-impaired face in the use of audio technologies in Buraidah city. The results also indicated the lack of financial allocations for educational technologies for the hearing-impaired, the difficulty of transferring technology inside the halls, the lack of Internet networks inside the halls, the insufficient training for teachers of the hearing-impaired. The study is similar to the current study of dealing with educational technologies for the hearing-impaired, and this study differs with the current study, as that study deals with the problems of teachers in the city of Buraidah, and the current study deals with the extent of development of educational technologies for the disabled and its role in improving the academic achievement.

Zamfirov&Saeva(2013) study aimed to identify the effect of educational technologies on the achievement of the hearing-impaired in the English language course in Bulgaria. The program was implemented for a year in 3 schools in the capital, Sofia, on students aged 16-23. After analyzing the results of the program, the study came out with several results, including the success of educational technologies in improving the level of academic achievement. The educational techniques contributed to improving the level of writing performance. The study used the experimental approach. The study is similar to the current study in terms of dealing with teaching techniques for the hearing-impaired and their impact on academic achievement. This study differs with the current study as the current study deals with the extent of development of education technologies for the hearing-impaired from a comparative perspective.

A study of Sharadqa and Zariqat (2012) aimed at discovering the effectiveness of an educational program by using educational techniques for speech training to develop an expressive language for a sample of (30) hearing-impaired students. The study used the experimental method. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences in the performance of the students on the total score of the post-measurement of the level of the expressive language in favor of the experimental group that underwent the program. Expressionism for the benefit of the age group, and the study is similar to the current study in dealing with teaching techniques for the hearing-impaired and this study differs with the current study as the current study deals with the extent of development of education technologies for the hearing-impaired and its role in improving academic achievement.

The study of Malkawi and Abu Alim (2010) aimed to find out the effectiveness of a technical program for training speech in the verbal method for the hearing impaired in kindergarten. The sample number reached (30) children and children, and the study tool consisted of three axes to train children in Arabic sounds and letters. The sounds of the Arabic letters were pronounced at the beginning and middle of the word, and the study used the experimental method, and the results indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the experimental and control group on the scale tool in favor of the current experimental study group. Where the current study deals with the extent of development of educational technologies for the hearing impaired in light of several international experiences and works to make use of them in improving academic achievement.

Hefni's study (2009) aimed at identifying the role of assistive technology in activating the goals of educating deaf students in inclusion institutes and programs. The study used the descriptive and analytical method. The analytical study reached several results, including that supportive technology can activate the goals of deaf education as it has many benefits for them, including reducing or eliminating the impact of disability, and enriching curricula, but teachers' use of this technology in educating the deaf is not as required. The study is similar to the current study in terms of it deals with technology supporting the hearing impaired and its role in achieving educational goals, including academic achievement. This study differs with the current study as the current study deals with the extent of development of education technologies for the hearing impaired in light of several international experiences and work to benefit from it in improving academic achievement.

Method and procedures

Members of the study

The study included (30) students with mild hearing impairment, their ages ranged between (4-7) years, who were intentionally chosen from the integrated schools in Jeddah, for reasons related to the continuity of training and good follow-up.

The study individuals were distributed randomly into two main groups: the first is an experimental group and the second is a control group, each group consisted of 15 male and female students, including children with mild hearing impairment, who were medically diagnosed in Jordanian government hospitals, and educationally through the integrated Schools for the Deaf affiliated with the Ministry of Education in Jeddah. Table (1) shows that.

Table (1)

Distribution of the study sample according to a variable (group, gender, and age)

Group	Gender	Age			Total
		4-5	5-6	6-7	
Control	Male	3	2	3	8

	Female	2	3	2	7
	Total	5	5	5	15
Experimental	Male	3	3	2	8
	Female	3	2	2	7
	Total	6	5	4	15
Total	Male	6	5	5	16
	Female	5	5	4	14
	Total	11	10	9	30

Study tools

First: the pre/ post test

Al-Amayyereh 's formal verbal expression scale was used (Al-Amayyereh, 1998), this test consists of (65) pictures, in which the subject sees the image and expresses it in verbal sound words. These pictures allow the participating students to provide correct phonetic samples in the Arabic language, and these words consist of (214) sounds. The scale is corrected by the number of votes that the examinee answered with sounds similar to those of adults, divided by the total number of votes, which is (214) votes multiplied by a hundred. The following equation illustrates that.

Student score = Total number of valid votes / Total number of votes x (100%)

Thus, this scale is used as a test to measure the sounds of the letters of the Arabic language with the movements of the short-tide, the long-term, and the syllables of letters and words. Colored pictures and games were used in order to obtain answers from each student. This test aims to establish standards for children's acquisition of consonants. The scale was modified on a sample of (180) children, whose ages ranged between two years and six years and four months, distributed among nine age groups (20) children. In each group, there are two equal distribution of males and females. Familiar pictures of the children of the sample were chosen, since the study aimed to measure spoken and linguistic abilities. The images were also modified to represent the prevalence of consonants, according to the results of the study conducted by the researcher and others on this topic. The test targeted the Arabic silences in three words sites: the beginning, middle and end of the word. The researcher made sure of the validity and reliability of the test. The test also showed the natural development of children, as the children's performance increased as they got older. The children's answers were analyzed twice: the first by comparing the answers with the formal form of the sound, and the second by taking the dialectal variation into account. The results are presented for each analysis.

The study determined the age at which children acquire each of the Arab silence. The researcher classified the votes according to the age of acquisition into three groups: early, medium and late. Whereas, early votes are acquired before the age of four years, while intermediate votes are acquired between the ages of four years, six years and eight months. The late votes would gain thereafter. It has been observed that there is a preference for the colloquial form of the sound at times, which makes it among the late sounds if we consider the formal form as a criterion for acquisition. There were no statistically significant individual differences between the performance of males and females in the study sample. One of the most important applications of the test is its wide use in the evaluation of children who suffer from delays or speech and language disorder, diagnosing their condition and building a treatment plan according to their performance on the test.

Scale Reliability

To verify the stability of the test, the reliability factor was calculated by applying the test - and re-applying the test (Test- R-Test) using the Pearson equation, two weeks after the first application, the application was made on a sample of (15) children with mild hearing impairment, who were selected from integrated schools in Jeddah, who were outside the sample of the study. The reliability coefficient was reached by calculating the test and its re-application (0.71). The researchers also used the Coder-Richardson equation (20) (KR-20). Which measures the internal consistency of the test items, and the overall stability factor was (0.76). These values were considered sufficient for the purposes of the study.

Second: the computer program (the expressive language development program)

Objective of the general program

This spoken educational computer program was developed with the aim of developing the expressive language skills of children with mild hearing impairment.

Special objectives of the program

- Helping parents of children with mild hearing impairment to understand the concept of expressive language disorder, and the foundations of the proposed program to treat this disorder.
- Helping children with mild hearing impairment to realize the importance of expressive language, and the impact that this has on healthy linguistic and social communication in their daily lives.

- Improving the ability of children with mild hearing impairment to use expressive language by recognizing letters and how to pronounce them (their sounds) and increasing the number of vocabularies, words and language structures they understand.
- Improving the ability of children with mild hearing impairment to respond correctly to verbal commands directed at them.
- Improve the ability of children with mild hearing impairment to understand vocabulary, and the pronunciation of letters and syllables.
- Emphasizing the role of children with mild hearing impairment as active participants in the treatment process.

This spoken educational computer program was developed with the aim of developing expressive language skills among children with mild hearing impairment. The computer program was designed by following the following steps:

- Review the literature related to the study problem. a study ((Karla, Leepir, and Stonell,(2010) and a study of (Cannon, 2010) and (Northern and downs, 2002) and others, with the aim of identifying the aspects of the language development of children aged 4-7 years.
- Designing the educational computer program for speech training in developing expressive language using one of the simple programs (Microsoft Power Point) This technique has been used because it is one of the simple computer technologies that any teacher of the hearing impaired, after training in using this technique, can use it, in addition, this type of computer-designed software serves this study in terms of taking into account the educational situation.

The program included the following main frameworks:

The first frame: It contains the opening screen of the program to introduce its content, and the general and specific objectives of this program.

The second frame: It contains a list of the lessons' titles in terms of entering the lesson by clicking on its title with the mouse cursor. Amal

Program interaction level

The program used the multimedia of sound, (letter, syllable, word) written, image, and movement, and the program enables the student to achieve the following goals:

1. Reading the written (letter, syllable, word) and expressing the image.
2. Listening to read the written (letter, syllable, word) in a child's voice adapts to the nature of the lessons.
3. Hover your mouse over the pictures and hear their sounds.
4. Provide feedback on the student's response on the same computerized images, and some computerized tests, in addition to appropriate positive reinforcement.

Study variables

First: the independent variables

A. The method, and it has two levels: the training program and the regular method.

B. Sex and has two levels, namely: male, female.

C. Age, and it has three levels: (4) years, (5) years, (6) years, (7) years.

Second: The dependent variable: It is the students' scores on the post-test.

Study Design and Statistical Treatment

The quasi-experimental approach was used in this study, where the study individuals were selected using the intentional sampling method. To answer the study's questions, the researchers used the design of the two unequal groups through a pre-test and a non-equivalent control. Group Pre-test and Post-test. The researchers used the design of the experimental group, Design and Control, and Figure (1) illustrates this.

To answer the study's questions, the following statistical methods were used: Arithmetic means and standard deviations to adjust (ANCOVA) and the one-size-fits-all analysis accompanying the comparisons (Scheffe) equivalence and increase the accuracy of the results.

Parity Procedures

To ensure the equivalence of the two study groups before the application of the study, the researcher applied the pre-expressive language development test to the study sample members, where the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the study sample's performance were calculated on the tribal expressive language development test as a whole and according to the group variable (control, And experimental), and Table (2) shows that.

Table 2: Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the performance of the study sample respondents on the Expressive Language Development Test

Group	N	Mean	Standard deviation
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Experimental	15	54.89	2.79
Control	15	53.08	2.35

* Maximum score (100)

It appears from the table that there are apparent differences between the tribal expressive averages as a whole and according to the group variable, as the arithmetic average of the performance of the control group students reached (53.08 and 54.89) for the performance of the experimental group students.

To know the mathematical significance of the performance of the study sample respondents on the statistical language development test for those differences; (T-test) was used for two independent groups (Independent Sample t-test) and Table (3) shows that.

Table 3: Test results (T) for two independent groups of averages for the performance of the study sample's response to the Expressive Language Development Test as a whole and according to the group variable

Group	N	Mean	Standard deviation	"T" value	df	Sig
Experimental	15	53.08	2.35	1.918	28	0.065
Control	15	54.89	2.79			

Table (3) shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the two average performance ($\alpha =$ at the level of statistical significance (0.05) of the study sample individuals on the Expressive Language Development Test as a whole attributable to the group variable, where the value ($t = 1.918$ in statistical significance) (0.065) It is greater than the level of significance, which indicates the parity of the two study groups; ($\alpha =$ statistical (0.05 (control, experimental)) on the Expressive Language Development Test as a whole.

Study Results

First: The results related to the first question, which states: "Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level = 0.05 (α) in expressive language development between the control group that did not undergo the computerized educational program and the experimental group that underwent the program?"

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the performance of the study sample individuals were calculated on the pre and post expressive language development test as a whole, in addition to the adjusted arithmetic averages for their scores on the posttest as a whole and according to the group variable (control and experimental), and Table (4) shows that.

Table (4) shows apparent differences between the arithmetic averages of the study sample's performance on the expressive language development test, as a whole. Resulting from the difference of the two study groups, and in order to verify the significance of these apparent differences; (ANCOVA) conducted an accompanying mono-expressive language development test as a whole and according to the group variable (control, experimental) after neutralizing the effect of the expressive language development test as a whole, as in Table (5).

Table 4: The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the performance of the study sample respondents on the pre and post expressive language development test as a whole, and the modified arithmetic averages for their scores on the posttest as a whole and according to the group variable (control, experimental)

Group	Pretest		Posttest		Modified	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Control	53.08	2.35	60.72	3.74	62.15	1.70
Experimental	54.89	2.79	75.33	9.92	73.89	1.70

Table 5: The results of the analysis of variance associated with the arithmetic averages of the performance of the study sample respondents on the dimensional expressive language development test as a whole and according to the group variable (control, experimental)

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	F value	Sig
Pre (accompanying)	470.653	1	470.653	11.520	0.002
Group	913.487	1	913.487	22.358	*0.000
ERROR	1103.138	27	40.857		
Total	2487.278	29			

Table (5) shows that there is a statistically significant difference at 0.05 between the two arithmetic averages = α) the modified level of statistical significance related to the performance of the study sample respondents on the post expressive language development test as a whole attributable to the two study groups and for the benefit of the experimental group students. Those who underwent an educational computer program, with an average arithmetic average (73.89) compared to an average arithmetic average of 62.15) for the performance of the control group. Where the value of (P =) (22,358) with statistical significance (0.000)

Second: The results related to the second question, which states: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) in the development of expressive language among the members of the experimental group due to the gender variable?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the performance of the members of the experimental group on the pre and post expressive language development test were calculated as a whole, in addition to the adjusted arithmetic averages for their scores on the posttest as a whole and according to the gender variable (male and female), and Table (6) shows that.

Table 6: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the performance of the experimental group's response to the pre- and post-expressive language development test as a whole, and the modified arithmetic averages for their scores on the post-test as a whole and according to the gender variable (male and female)

Gender	Pretest		Posttest		Modified	
	*mean	Standard error	*mean	Standard error	*mean	Standard error
Male	55.43	1.71	75.70	10.45	73.98	1.86
Female	54.27	3.73	74.90	10.09	76.86	1.99

Table (6) shows that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the expressive language development test of the dimensional language as a whole. Resulting from the difference in the sex of the individuals of the experimental group, and in order to verify the significance of these apparent differences; An analysis of variance was performed on the one-dimensional expressive language development test (ANCOVA) as a whole and according to the gender variable (male, female) after neutralizing the effect of the Expressive Language Development Test as a whole, as in Table 7.

Table (7): Results of the analysis of variance associated with the arithmetic averages of the performance of the experimental group's response to the post-expressive language development test as a whole and according to the gender variable (male and female)

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	F value	Sig
Pre (accompanying)	1049.508	1	1049.508	38.680	0.000
Gender	29.577	1	29.577	1.090	0.317
Error	325.596	12	27.133		

Table (7) shows that there is no statistically significant difference (0.05) between the two averages = α) at the level of statistical significance. For male performance (73.98) versus a modified arithmetic average (76.86) for female performance. Where the value of (P = 1.090) statistically significant (0.317).

Third: The results related to the third question, which states: = α) "Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance 0.05) in the development of expressive language among the members of the experimental group due to the variable of age? To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the performance of the members of the experimental group were calculated on the pre and post expressive language development test as a whole, in addition to the modified arithmetic averages for their scores on the posttest as a whole and according to the age variable, and Table (8) shows that:

Table (8): The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the performance of the experimental group's response to the pre- and post-expressive language development test as a whole, and the modified arithmetic averages for their scores on the post-test as a whole and according to the age variable

Age	Pretest		Posttest		Modified	
	*mean	Standard error	*mean	Standard error	*mean	Standard error

5-4	52.26	2.12	64.56	2.24	64.54	1.25
6-5	55.51	0.51	78.50	1.65	78.51	0.88
7-6	58.06	0.80	87.50	1.04	87.53	1.52

Table (9) shows the existence of apparent differences between the arithmetic averages of the performance of the members of the experimental group on the post-expressive language development test as a whole. Resulting from the difference in the age variable, and in order to verify the significance of these apparent differences; Concomitant single-factor variance analysis was performed (ANCOVA) On testing the development of the post expressive language as a whole and according to the age variable after neutralizing the effect of the test for developing the expressive language of expression as a whole, as in the table.

Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the two researchers recommended a number of recommendations that can be summarized as follows:

- The educational officials' adoption of educational computer programs to develop expressive language for students with mild hearing impairment.
- Holding training courses for teachers to train on computer programs for speech training in developing expressive language, targeting children with minor hearing impairments.
- The need to prepare other computer programs targeting all types of language disorders, as the results of studies have shown the effectiveness of this program.
- Conducting studies dealing with educational computer programs for the development of expressive language that shed light on other age groups of students with minor hearing disabilities, such as studying age groups from 8 to 12 years old.
- Conducting studies similar to this one by using other tools such as observation, interviewing, choosing a larger sample size, and another area.

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Author Information

Dr. Lina Bin Saddiq

Associate Professor of Special Education at Special Education Department, Educational Higher Studies Program, King Abdul Aziz University
